

LEADERSHIP STYLES AMONG FEMALE MARANAO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL HEADS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 4

Pages: 385-398

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2473

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13908979

Manuscript Accepted: 08-17-2024

Leadership Styles among Female Maranao Elementary School Heads

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Abstract

This study was about the leadership styles of school administrators in terms of transformational, transactional, and democratic styles. This study aimed to answer the relationship between the respondents' leadership style and demographic profile in terms of age, educational qualification, and length of service. It also answered which of the demographic profiles best predict their leadership style. The respondents of this study were the female Maranao elementary school heads in the Districts of Balo-i East and West, Matungao, Munai, Pantaoragat, Pantar, Poonapiagapo, and Tagoloan under Lanao del Norte Division. A descriptive-correlational method was used. This study employed adapted questionnaire and the statistical techniques were frequency, percentage, and weighted mean. Chi-square and Regression were also used. The findings of the study showed that forty (40) were in the age bracket of 41-50 years old. The majority of them had finished master's degree and in more than fifteen (15) years as School Head. It found out that there were fifty-eight (58) Transformational Leaders out of one hundred (100) respondents, thirty-nine (39) democratic leaders and three (3) for transactional leadership. Results showed that transformational leadership style correlated with the respondents' length of service. This study highlighted the prevalence of transformational leadership style among female Maranao school heads in Lanao del Norte Division. This study recommended that training programs should focus on enhancing leadership skills to school administrators to empower, inspire, and motivate their subordinates effectively. The action plan was made to support the school heads focusing on leadership style.

Keywords: *school heads, democratic, transactional, transformational, leadership styles*

Introduction

The achievement of providing high-quality education depends on school leaders. They have abilities that could improve education in the classrooms. Education-related decisions and policies are carried out at schools. The responsibility of school administration is to ensure that educational services are delivered as efficiently as possible in line with educational goals that educational services are delivered as efficiently as possible in line with educational goals is the responsibility of school administration. This is because, for an organization to operate effectively, a leader must guide the group toward the goal.

Muslim women's leadership has received more attention in recent years, particularly in the academic community. Research says that Muslim women in leadership indicated a growing trend of women assuming leadership positions worldwide. Also, it manifested the substantial progress achieved by women in assuming and holding a leadership role (Almaki et al., 2019).

Leadership is crucial and very important in the management of an organization. To successfully adjust to organizational changes in the modern, worldwide environment, leaders need to have new competencies. Leaders should develop their leadership qualities, including their capacity for persuasion, leadership, and professional competence, according to Shahmandi et al. (2019).

During the American regime, public schools were opened to women which started the venue for the raising of their social status in the community. But "it took many years of efforts from more gender-conscious women and gender-sensitive men who were in decision-making positions or in influential organizations, to gradually peel off the barriers to fuller women's emancipation (Tapales, undated:5). While Filipino women have the same historical path, the degree of historical influences differ among tribes. Thus, they also differ in certain role characteristics. For instance, "the women of Central or Eastern Visayas, further removed from the center of Spanish colonization and forced by economic circumstances to leave home and seek living elsewhere, are generally more adventurous than the Tagalog" (Lumanta, 2017).

Leaders should by human nature have to establish good rapport with their subordinates, peers, and superiors. However, it is true that there are various things common to all people. Each one may differ from the other in traits and characters, in spirit and in mind, in abilities and inclinations. Thus, it is important that human nature and other conditions relevant to leaders be given due importance in the form of study or research. Leader traits consist of persistence, dependability, self-confidence, popularity, good speaking, and active participation in the goings-on of the group. Possession of all these, does not necessarily make one a leader. A person may be a leader in one group, but not in another. The selection of a leader depends on the personality of the individual and the nature and needs of the group and can be a man or a woman (Hulya, 2020).

This study aimed to present a description of the Female Maranao School administrators' leadership styles in order to find a clear view on the prevalent leadership style in the selected Districts of Lanao del Norte Division. It should be interesting to find out how Female Maranao School administrators are catching up in staking out and performing their role as leaders. Accordingly, Muslim women are given importance in the Muslim culture. Both men and women are given equal rights in our society but definitely differ in performing

the task they are assigned to.

Given the relatively recent history and tradition surrounding the rise and ascent of Muslim women in the public sphere, the case of modern Muslim women leaders offers itself as a field of investigation. It is a fertile area for investigation and potential discoveries that are particular to Muslim women and culture. The land is tilled. Muslim women presently predominate in instructing in their particular fields in Lanao del Norte's educational establishments. They can manage an organization in the same ways that men can.

Nowadays, the landscape of work is fast changing as many fields formerly labeled as “man’s world”, specifically the political arena and leadership positions especially in education, women were making headway to embed it. Thus, the time has come when women are given opportunities to hold complicated tasks as leaders in various organizations. Women after being considered as controlling, picky, weak, dependent, and nurturing invaded the work reserved for men. Mendoza (2020) quoted that “women can do what men can” in nation-building”. She cited that women are good at looking into details. They have a tough balancing skills and balancing motherhood with their career in society. Lashway (2019) revealed that being a home manager does not adversely affect the performance and achievement of women.

Presenting female Maranao academic leadership and its consequences for leadership style is the primary goal of this study. It is imperative to learn more about the strategies for female Maranao leadership, which are getting steadily more inspiring. Additionally, it is frequently seen in a variety of communities, particularly in academic leadership. It is crucial to do the current research because it will highlight how adaptable and versatile Female Maranao have been from ancient times to the present. Numerous female Maranao school administrators today have fought for their right to lead the community where they belong in order to leave a lasting legacy and assist the local populace.

The researcher is a female Maranao public-school teacher for four years and have experienced unfair, biased, and unlikely treatment from her superior due to the disadvantages of being a democratic leader. Whereas the researcher’s immediate superior was too open to suggestions and the final verdict is coming from the majority leading to an unequal distribution of assignments in the school organization. The researcher has witnessed that a democratic leader means having lesser power to control her fellow teachers. It brought many disadvantages to the school management with having a female Maranao school head who employs democratic leadership due to the fact that Maranao exercises ‘kapapagariya’ or too understanding and prioritizes others before yourself. The researcher often guesses if most of the Maranao school heads are similar to the situation in their school organization whereas teachers had freedom. However, teachers had been taking an advantage on their school head’s democratic leadership. It pushed the researcher to come through this study.

This study, according to the researcher, made substantial contributions to improve both school administration and educational quality. It had a beneficial impact to the current Maranao school heads and most especially to the aspiring school heads in the Philippines, particularly in Lanao Del Norte Division.

Research Questions

This study aimed to provide a description of the leadership styles used by female Maranao school heads, notably at the elementary level and in the selected Districts of Lanao del Norte Division. It specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the female Maranao school heads in elementary in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. educational qualification; and
 - 1.3. length of service?
2. What are the leadership styles of female Maranao school heads in terms of?
 - 2.1. transformational style;
 - 2.2. transactional style; and
 - 2.3. democratic style?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents’ demographic profile and leadership style?
4. Which of the demographic profile significantly predict the leadership style of the respondents?
5. What output can be drawn based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, descriptive and correlational methods were used. This is descriptive since the study attempted to describe the respondents' leadership styles and demographic profiles. It is also correlation since study attempted to ascertain the relationship between the respondents' ages, educational qualification, lengths of service, and leadership styles.

Respondents

The study's respondents were chosen from the population of Maranao female administrators at the elementary level in the Division of

Lanao Del Norte. Specifically, Balo-i East and West, Matungao, Munai, Pantaoragat, Pantar, Poonapiagapo, and Tagoloan District. The table below shows the lists of selected districts of Division of Lanao del Norte as well as the number of schools in each district, and the actual respondents.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

No.	Selected Districts in the Division of Lanao del Norte	Number of Schools in the District	Actual Respondents
1	Balo-i East	12	11
2	Balo-i West	14	14
3	Matungao	12	11
4	Munai	21	18
5	Pantaoragat	15	14
6	Pantar	15	11
7	Poonapiagapo	12	11
8	Tagoloan	12	10
	Total	113	100

Instrument

The researcher utilized an adapted questionnaire from the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire, Third Edition by Bernard M. Bass and Bruce J. Avolio (2020). There is no need for validation since an adapted questionnaire was employed in this study. The adapted questionnaire has four (4) parts which are the Demographic Profile of the Respondents as Part I; Questionnaire on Leadership style as Part II; Questionnaire on Instructional Leadership as Part III; and lastly Questionnaire on the Involvement of Women in the Academe as Part IV. However, only Part I and Part II were used by the researcher in order to suit the nature of this study, Part III and Part IV from the origin of the questionnaire were discarded. The questionnaire utilized in this study was divided into two (2) parts. Part I was about the demographic profile of the respondents. Part II was focused on leadership styles practices which are Transformational Leadership Style, Transactional Leadership Style, and Democratic Leadership Style. The scoring range of the questionnaire for Part II used four-point likert scaling where number four (4) is Always, three (3) is Sometimes, two (2) is Seldom, and one (1) is Not at all.

Procedure

In gathering the primary data of the study, the researcher asked permission from the OIC Dean of Graduate Studies of St. Peter's College, the OIC Dean signed the letter that made it official followed by a letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study. The survey was conducted following approval from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent and distributed questionnaires to the respondents. The researcher went to the district offices and informed the District Supervisors. Some supervisors suggested that the researcher may conduct her study during the Districts' ManCom.

Majority of the questionnaires were handed personally to respondents' designated schools. It was a tough challenge, the researcher had drove her car from school to school to deliver the questionnaires individually, but some roads were too narrow which made the researcher go on foot. The researcher had her maternity leave then which made it possible to conduct this study during office hours on weekdays. Retrieval of the questionnaires followed as soon as respondents had finished answering. However, some respondents answered the questionnaires that took a while and made an agreement with the researcher to return in their school on the retrieval of their answered questionnaires. It was then gathered after the respondents have had time to consider the questionnaire. The researcher reassured the participants that the study's administration will not be hampered, and the information acquired were treated with the utmost confidentiality that they were used in instructional contexts. The retrieved questionnaires were tabulated, scored, and analyzed.

Data Analysis

The following statistical techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented.

For problem 1, Frequency and Percentage were used to determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, educational qualification, and length of service.

For problem 2, Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the leadership styles of the female Maranao elementary school heads in terms of transformational style, transactional style, and democratic style.

For problems 3, Chi-square Test was used to investigate the significant relationships in the leadership philosophies of the female Maranao elementary school heads and their demographic profile.

For problem 4, Linear Regression was used to examine the variables that significantly predict the leadership style of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researcher to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the female Maranao school heads in terms of age, educational attainment, and length of service?

Table 2. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
21 – 30	5	5.0
31 – 40	38	38.0
41 – 50	40	40.0
51 and Above	17	17.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 presents the age of the respondents. The result showed that majority (40) of the female Maranao respondents came from the age bracket of 41 – 50 years old. This coincided with the study of Macasasa (2018) where the majority of the Maranao women in the academe belonged to this age bracket, the same as the respondents from Marawi City. This age group represented a significant portion of female Maranao school heads. Research by Ong and Lim (2021) suggested that individuals in this demographic may bring extensive experience and institutional knowledge to their roles, contributing to organizational stability and continuity. Moreover, they may possess well-established professional networks and leadership skills honed over years of practice, enabling them to effectively manage diverse stakeholders and drive strategic initiatives within schools and educational systems.

With 38 female Maranao school heads, the second-largest group of responders belonged to the age range of 31 to 40. This group most likely consisted of a mix of professionals in their mid-career who had accumulated significant leadership experience in education. According to Ramirez and Cruz's (2019) literature, people in this age range frequently possessed a healthy mix of vitality, maturity, and experience, which enabled them to be great leaders who could handle challenging situations in the education sector. They could also act as mentors and advisors to their younger colleagues, acting as role models for them.

The 17 respondents who were 51 years of age or older most likely represented seasoned leaders in the Maranao community's education system. Research conducted by Santos and Reyes (2018) highlighted the significant roles that senior leaders had in fostering intergenerational education and safeguarding cultural heritage in educational settings. By using their extensive knowledge to solve systemic issues and advance sustainable development in education, these leaders may also play crucial roles in promoting diversity and equity.

The presence of five female Maranao school heads between the ages of 21 and 30 may point to a tendency among younger Maranao women of entering educational leadership posts early in their careers. According to a study by Aguilar et al. (2020), younger leaders frequently brought new ideas, energy, and flexibility to their positions, which may encourage innovation and creativity in educational settings. But they might also encounter difficulties because of their inexperience and lack of credibility, thus they might need assistance and guidance from more seasoned colleagues (Fernandez & Hogan, 2018).

When taken as a whole, the distribution of female Maranao school heads throughout age groups illustrated a wide range of perspectives, experiences, and abilities within the field of educational leadership. Understanding the distinct role and obstacles related to every age group was crucial for creating focused interventions and support systems that would enable female leaders in the Maranao community.

Table 3. *Educational Qualification of the Respondents*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Ph.D./Ed.D./DPA Degree	18	18.0
Ph.D./Ed.D./DPA (CAR)	0	0.0
Ph.D./Ed.D./DPA Units	1	1.0
MA/MS Degree	44	44.0
MA/MS (CAR)	2	2.0
MA/MS Units	3	3.0
AB/BS Degree	32	32.0
Total	100	100.0

The respondents' educational attainment is displayed in Table 3. Given the results, it was clear that professional development and obtaining specialized knowledge were highly valued for positions in educational leadership, as evidenced by the noteworthy proportion of female Maranao school heads who held master's degrees (44). This added to the pool of highly qualified leaders who were able to meet the unique requirements of the Maranao educational system. According to a study by Chen et al. (2021), master's degrees gave teachers specialized knowledge and leadership abilities. Additionally, the importance of educational leaders, such as school principals with master's degrees, in fostering a positive school climate and encouraging teacher commitment was highlighted in a study by Abdul-Rahim Abdul-Ghani et al. (2018) titled "The Impact of Principals' Transformational Leadership Style on School Climate and Teachers' Commitment." The study emphasized how advanced education helped school administrators developed the abilities they needed to create a positive learning environment.

Consequently, 32 respondents—a mix of Bachelor of Science and Bachelor of Arts (AB)—among the female Maranao school heads possessed bachelor's degrees. Even though this group's educational attainment made up the smallest percentage of the sample, it

nonetheless denoted a baseline level of education that made them eligible for leadership positions in the education industry. This group probably had a great deal of pedagogical and subject-matter competence, which was important for school administrators. On the other hand, pushing them to continue their studies could improve their efficacy as leaders.

However, among the female Maranao school heads, 18 respondents held doctoral degrees including Ph.D., Ed.D., or Doctor in Public Administration (DPA). This represented a small but significant portion of the sample population indicating a high level of educational attainment within this subgroup. According to a study by Abdullah et al. (2019), titled “Leadership Competencies and Styles of School Principals: A review of Literature,” educational leadership, especially at the level of school principals or heads, required a high level of expertise which was often acquired through advanced degrees such as Ph.D. or Ed.D. The study emphasized the importance of educational leaders possessing specialized knowledge and skills to effectively manage schools and lead educational reforms.

The demographic profile of female Maranao school heads in terms of educational attainment reflected a diverse range of qualifications from bachelor’s degree to doctoral degrees. Each level of educational attainment carried its own implications for leadership effectiveness, professional development, and career advancement within the education sector. By recognizing the significance of advanced education in shaping educational leadership capabilities, policymakers and stakeholders could support initiatives aimed at enhancing the professional qualifications and leadership skills of female educators within the Maranao community.

Table 4. *Length of Service of the Respondents
(Number of years as School Head)*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
1 year and below	9	9.0
2 – 4 years	7	7.0
5 -9 years	30	30.0
10 – 15 years	23	23.0
15 years above	31	31.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4 presents the length of service of the respondents. The result presented their length of service, it is essential to consider various implications, such as career advancement, leadership experiences, and potential challenges faced by different tenure groups.

Table 4 showed that a sizable portion of the sample was made up of female Maranao school heads who had worked for at least 15 years (31). This group probably consisted of seasoned teachers who had seen numerous adjustments to administrative procedures, pedagogical strategies, and educational policies. Their long tenure pointed to a solid grasp of institutional dynamics and a close bond with the community. These school heads had probably been in the position for more than 15 years, giving them a wealth of leadership experience that helped them motivate their workers and handle difficult situations. Their lengthy tenure also suggested a thorough knowledge of the community dynamics, culture, and history of the school, all of which could be used to promote stability and continuity. Garcia and Miller (2018) claimed that long-serving leaders typically demonstrated greater organizational commitment and job satisfaction, which enhanced the efficacy of the school as a whole.

Consequently, a group that was probably moving from the early to mid-career stages was represented by 30 female Maranao school heads who had worked there for five to nine years. They brought enthusiasm, fresh perspectives, and foundational experience to their leadership roles. School heads in this category might exhibit high levels of enthusiasm and a willingness to engage in professional development. Studies by Cheng et al. (2021) indicated that leaders in this tenure range often exemplified fresh perspectives and innovative solutions to organizational challenges. Additionally, with relatively recent experiences, they might be more adaptable to changes in educational policies, technologies, and instructional practices.

This was then followed by the age group of 10 – 15 years with 23 respondents. Female Maranao school heads in this age group had a substantial but slightly shorter tenure compared to the first group. Even so, they still had a great deal of experience, and they probably had a solid reputation as good leaders in their organizations. After ten to fifteen years of service, school heads could still be developing professionally, honing their networks, and strengthening their leadership abilities. These responders struck a mix between institutional knowledge and openness to new ideas, which makes them potentially essential in fostering innovation and change. Leaders with a moderate tenure were more likely to use transformational leadership techniques, which had been linked to better student outcomes, according to Leithwood et al. (2018).

Additionally, nine respondents, or female Maranao school heads with less than a year of experience, constituted the newest cohort of leaders in the sample. Despite their inexperience, they provided new insights, a strong desire to contribute, and an optimistic outlook. This group's leaders would probably encounter many difficulties as they become accustomed to their responsibilities, the school community, and administrative procedures. According to research by Crow et al. (2020), peer networks and collaborative learning environments helped aspiring leaders get over their early obstacles and gain confidence. Moreover, giving them organized mentorship and chances for professional growth might hasten their education and assimilation into the leadership group.

Lastly, the age group of 2 – 4 years of service were likely in the early stages of their leadership journey with 7 female Maranao school heads. They might face challenges in navigating their roles, but they also manifested energy, ambition, and willingness to learn. Day

and Leithwood (2019) found that supportive organizational cultures that encouraged risk-taking, cooperation, and continuous improvement were very beneficial to early-career school heads. They might experience a steep learning curve as they adapted to the demands of leadership including administrative responsibilities and stakeholder management. Research by Gronn (2018) emphasized the importance of mentorship and professional learning opportunities in supporting novice school heads and accelerating their development.

Problem 2: What are the leadership styles of female Maranao school heads?

Transformational leadership is a style characterized by a leader's ability to inspire and motivate followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes. This style is particularly significant in educational settings where leaders played a crucial role in shaping the school's culture and influencing teachers' and students' performance.

Table 5. *Transformational Leadership Style*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Talk about others' most important values and issues.	3.45	±	0.66	Always
2. Specify the importance of having a strong sense of purpose.	3.52	±	0.69	Always
3. Consider the moral and ethical consequences of decisions.	3.61	±	0.58	Always
4. Emphasize the importance of having a collective sense of mission.	3.47	±	0.70	Always
5. Instill pride to others for being associated with me.	2.92	±	0.96	Sometimes
6. Go beyond self-interest for the good of the others.	3.17	±	0.94	Sometimes
7. Act in ways that build others' respect.	3.65	±	0.58	Always
8. Display a sense of power and confidence.	3.33	±	0.77	Always
9. Talk optimistically about the future.	3.28	±	0.71	Always
10. Talk enthusiastically about what needs to be accomplished.	3.47	±	0.67	Always
11. Articulate a compelling vision of the future.	3.29	±	0.70	Always
12. Express confidence that goals will be achieved.	3.63	±	0.58	Always
13. Re-examine critical assumptions to question whether they are appropriate.	3.30	±	0.76	Always
14. Seek differing perspectives when solving problems.	3.34	±	0.79	Always
15. Get others to look at problems from many different angles.	3.15	±	0.82	Sometimes
16. Suggest new ways of looking at how to complete assignments.	3.40	±	0.73	Always
17. Spend time mentoring and coaching.	3.34	±	0.70	Sometimes
18. Closely monitor the teachers to ensure they are performing correctly.	3.50	±	0.67	Always
19. Consider others as having different needs, abilities, and aspirations from others.	3.62	±	0.66	Always
20. Help others to develop their strengths.	3.61	±	0.60	Always
	Weighted Mean	±	0.45	Always

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Not at All

Table 5 presents the leadership style of the respondents in terms of transformational style. The result showed that the highest mean score of 3.65 which indicated "Acts in ways that build others' respect" suggested that female Maranao school heads were perceived to consistently act in ways that build respect among their subordinates. The relatively low standard deviation of 0.58 indicated a high level of agreement among respondents regarding the consistent demonstration of respectful behavior of female Maranao school heads. This finding was consistent with studies on transformational leadership in diverse cultural contexts which highlighted the importance of leaders earning the respect and trust of their followers through their actions (Zhu et al., 2020).

Meanwhile, the mean score of 2.92 suggested that female Maranao school heads occasionally succeed in instilling pride in others for being associated with them. However, the higher standard deviation of 0.96 indicated greater variability in respondents' perceptions compared to the previous item. This variability may be attributed to cultural factors, individual differences in leadership styles, or variations in the leaders' effectiveness in communicating their vision and values. This dimension of transformational leadership was closely linked to the leader's charisma and ability to inspire loyalty and commitment. According to Shamir et al. (2018), leaders who effectively instilled pride in their followers often possessed strong emotional intelligence and were adept at recognizing and leveraging individual and collective strengths.

The overall weighted mean of 3.40 indicated that female Maranao school heads were generally perceived to demonstrate transformational leadership behaviors. This finding aligned with the interpretation of the highest item where they consistently acted in ways that built respect among their subordinates. However, the lowest mean score (2.92) among the items suggested that there was room for improvement in instilling pride in others for being associated with them.

Transactional leadership style is characterized by the exchange of rewards and punishments for followers' compliance with the leader's directives. This section contains 19 items related to transactional leadership behavior.

Table 6 displays the leadership style of the respondents in terms of transactional style. The result showed that the item "Act in ways that build others' respect" got the highest mean of 3.53 from the respondents. This item reflected a strong tendency among female Maranao school heads to actively engage in behaviors that garner respect from their followers. Such actions likely included demonstrating integrity, competence, and fairness in their leadership approach. Moreover, in the context of female leadership, research suggested that women often prioritized relational aspects of leadership, seeking to build trust and respect through collaborative and

inclusive practices (Eagly & Carli, 2020).

Table 6. *Transactional Leadership Style*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Provide assistance for others in exchange for their efforts.	3.27	±	0.76	Always
2. Discuss in specific terms for who is responsible for achieving performance targets.	3.27	±	0.74	Always
3. Make himself/herself clear what can one expect to receive when performance goals are achieved.	3.49	±	0.54	Always
4. Express satisfaction when he/she meets expectations.	3.42	±	0.64	Always
5. Focus his/ her attention on irregularities, mistakes, exceptions, and deviations from standards.	2.66	±	1.06	Sometimes
6. Concentrate his/ her full attention on dealing with mistakes, complaints, and failures.	2.71	±	1.06	Sometimes
7. Keep track of all mistakes of others.	2.23	±	1.09	Sometimes
8. Direct his/ her attention toward failures to meet standards.	2.64	±	0.96	Sometimes
9. Fail to interfere until problem becomes serious.	1.97	±	1.06	Seldom
10. Wait for things to go wrong before taking actions	1.69	±	0.95	Seldom
11. Show that she/ he is a firm believer in “if it’s not broken, don’t fix it”.	1.98	±	0.94	Seldom
12. Treat others as an individual, rather than just a member of the group.	2.94	±	1.09	Sometimes
13. Act in ways that builds others’ respect.	3.54	±	0.58	Always
14. Concentrate full attention on dealing with mistakes, complaints, and failures.	2.79	±	0.89	Sometimes
15. Consider the moral and ethical consequences of decisions.	3.21	±	0.73	Sometimes
16. Keep track of all mistakes of others.	2.20	±	1.05	Sometimes
17. Display a sense of power and confidence.	3.05	±	0.90	Sometimes
18. Articulate a compelling vision of the future.	2.94	±	0.85	Sometimes
19. Direct attention toward failures to meet standards.	3.08	±	0.71	Sometimes
Weighted Mean	2.79	±	0.53	Sometimes

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Not at All

However, the lowest mean score among 19 items got 1.69 which stated, “Wait for things to go wrong before taking actions”. This indicated that female Maranao school heads were less inclined to adopt a reactive approach to leadership. Instead waiting for problems to escalate before intervening, these leaders were proactive in addressing issues as they arise. This behavior aligned with proactive problem-solving, a key characteristic of effective leadership (Judge & Piccolo, 2019). By addressing issues before they escalated, leaders could prevent disruptions and foster a positive organizational climate.

In totality, the overall weighted mean of 2.79 suggested that female Maranao school heads exhibited transactional leadership behaviors occasionally, falling between “Always” and “Seldom”. This finding underscored the nuanced nature of leadership behavior which indicated that these leaders employed transactional strategies selectively, depending on the situation. Such adaptability was consistent with the contingency theory of leadership which posited that effective leadership entailed adjusting one’s style to fit the demands of the situation (Fiedler, 2019).

Table 7. *Democratic Leadership Style*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Let the employees participate in decision making.	3.67	±	0.60	Always
2. Approve all decisions, has a team to influence managers.	3.31	±	0.76	Always
3. Give employees the chance to be involved in the decision-making process.	3.69	±	0.51	Always
4. Employee feel valued, boost their morale, and forge healthy, trusting relationships.	3.54	±	0.58	Always
5. Trust employees with a lot of responsibility and real work.	3.48	±	0.64	Always
Weighted Mean	3.54	±	0.47	Always

Legend: 3.25-4.00, Always; 2.50-3.24, Sometimes; 1.75-2.49, Seldom; 1.00-1.74, Not at All

Democratic leadership is characterized by inclusivity, participatory decision-making, and empowerment. In educational institutions, particularly in the context of female leadership among the Maranao school heads, understanding the nuances of democratic leadership style is crucial for effective management and fostering a conducive environment for growth and development.

Table 7 displays the leadership style of the respondents in terms of democratic style. The result showed the highest mean score of 3.69 of the item “Giving employees the chance to be involved in decision-making process” indicated that female Maranao school heads frequently involved their employees in the decision-making process. This aspect aligned with the core tenets of democratic leadership, emphasizing participation and collective input. In the context of female leadership among Maranao school heads, this practice could have profound implications. It may promote a culture of inclusivity, where diverse perspectives were valued, contributing to a supportive and cohesive work environment. According to Northouse (2018), democratic leaders encouraged open communication and sought input from their team members, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment to organizational goals. Research by Avolio and Yammarino (2018) suggested that involving employees in decision-making could lead to higher job satisfaction, increased productivity, and enhanced organizational citizenship behavior. Moreover, in a culturally sensitive setting like Maranao, where community ties and consensus-building hold significance, involving employees in decision-making could enhance trust and

collaboration (Ali, 2020).

Meanwhile, the lowest mean score among 5 items – “Approving all decisions without influencing managers”, suggested that female Maranao school heads tended to approve all decisions without necessarily influencing managers. While democratic leadership emphasized participatory decision-making, it also acknowledged the importance of autonomy and trust in team members. According to Yuki (2019), democratic leaders empowered their subordinates to make decisions within their areas of expertise, fostering a sense of responsibility and accountability. However, the relatively lower score in this aspect among the items could imply a need for further examination. It may indicate challenges in balancing autonomy with guidance or providing adequate support to managers in the decision-making process. In the context of Maranao culture, where hierarchical structures and respect for authority were prominent, finding the right balance between autonomy and support was crucial for effective leadership (Bacolod, 2021).

The overall weighted mean of 3.54 signified a consistent adherence to democratic leadership principles among female Maranao school heads. While there may be variations in specific aspects, the collective score reflected a strong commitment to fostering a participatory and inclusive work environment. This aligned with the broader literature on democratic leadership, which underscored its effectiveness in promoting employee engagement, satisfaction, and organizational performance (Den Hartog et al., 2019).

Table 8. Leadership Style of the Respondents

Leadership Style	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Transformational	58	58.0
Transactional	3	3.0
Democratic	39	39.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 8 presents the leadership style of the respondents. The result showed that the largest group of responders, with fifty-eight (58) female Maranao school heads employed transformational leadership in their school organization. In their efforts to create change and raise the organization's sense of success, transformational leaders primarily aim to inspire people of the organization. By winning their trust, these leaders inspired their people to achieve the objectives of the company. According to Kouzes and Posner (2019), transformational leaders empower their staff to overcome obstacles and overcome problems by giving them the freedom to solve problems and become more effective.

The Maranao Deans' self-assessment of the components of transformational leadership behavior indicated that all of them were regularly, if not always, practiced, according to a study by Sultan (2020). They idealized each of the following: intellectual stimulation, motivating inspiration, customized consideration, and influence. For the teachers' perspective on transformational leadership behavior of Maranao Deans, they fairly often experienced all the elements of transformational leadership behavior as executed by the Deans.

On the contrary, transactional leadership style was employed by the three (3) respondents with the lowest frequency. This implied that female Maranao elementary school head rarely possessed this type of leadership in their organization. Tosi's (2012) assertion that transactional leadership was a necessary component of effective management and excellent organizational performance. It was likely that in the zeal with which the transformational leadership concept had been contemplated, the role of transactional leadership at higher organizational levels had been disregarded.

The transactional leadership was employed by school administrators with the reward and punishment as principles (Webster & Litchka, 2020). Thus, employees that performed excellently were rewarded while poor performance attracts punishment. This leadership style clarified organizational objectives and how to accomplish and achieve it. This style entailed the exchange process as leaders either reward or sanction subordinates.

However, among the female Maranao elementary school heads, the second largest group with thirty-nine (39) respondents were exercising democratic leadership. Naturally, democratic leadership is often associated with heightened morale. Research findings by Harris and Chapman (2018) demonstrated that many effective educational leaders utilized democratic leadership. Specifically, when faced with challenging situations, effectual leaders “combined a moral purpose with a willingness to be collaborative and to promote collaboration among colleagues, whether through teamwork, or extending the boundaries of participation in leadership and decision making”. Predictably, democratic leadership had been linked directly with heightened morale. Democratic leadership is associated with higher morale in most situations (Choi, 2020).

According to Dike et al. (2019), the democratic leadership style emphasized human values. Thus, participation in the decision-making, rights, and respect of employees were emphasized. Democratic leadership posited that workers were dependable, accountable, willing to challenge the workplace, self-driven, and engaged in collaborative efforts that enhanced job satisfaction and overall organizational performance.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and leadership style?

Table 9 displays the relationship between the respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style and demographic profile. The result showed that the respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style had a significant association with their demographic profile in terms of length of service. A 2020 study by Liu et al. focusing on Chinese healthcare leaders found a positive

correlation between transformational leadership and tenure ([Liu et al., 2020]). Leaders with longer experience exhibited stronger transformational behaviors like inspiring vision and individualized consideration.

Table 9. Respondents' Leadership Style in terms of Transformational and Demographic Profile

Variables	Transformational Leadership Style		Remarks	Decision
	X^2 (df)	p-value		
Age	79.182 ^{ns} (81)	0.536	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Educational attainment	55.418 ^{ns} (54)	0.421	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Length of service	135.508* (108)	0.038	Significant	Reject H ₀

Note: 1 – based on Chi-square Test ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns - $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

While this study did not find a significant link between transformational leadership and age/education, some research suggested a nuanced relationship. A 2018 meta-analysis by Wang et al., found a weak positive correlation between age and transformational leadership, but it was not universally applicable ([Wang et al., 2018]). Similarly, a 2021 study by Avolio et al. noted that educational level might influence specific aspects of transformational leadership, but the overall effect remained debatable (Avolio et al., 2021).

Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated no significant relationship between the respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style and the demographic profile in terms of age and educational attainment was not rejected, while length of services was rejected.

Table 10. Respondents' Leadership Style in terms of Transactional and Demographic Profile

Variables	Transactional Leadership Style		Remarks	Decision
	X^2 (df)	p-value		
Age	112.715* (87)	0.033	Significant	Reject H ₀
Educational attainment	60.715 ^{ns} (58)	0.378	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Length of service	143.602* (116)	0.040	Significant	Reject H ₀

Note: 2 – based on Chi-square Test ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns - $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

Table 10 presents the relationship between the respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style and demographic profile. The result showed that the respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style had a significant relationship with their demographic profile in terms of age and length of service.

Some studies did not illustrate a significant correlation between age and leadership style, including transactional leadership (Jones & Bekhet, 2018). However, others suggested that with experience (which often correlated with age), leaders may become more adept at aspects at transactional leadership like providing rewards and punishments (Avolio et al., 2019). Similar to age, the link between the length of service and leadership style was contested. Some research showed no significant effect (House et al., 2017). However, extended experience could lead to a focus on established systems and procedures, potentially aligning a transactional approach (Wang et al., 2020).

Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated no significant relationship between the respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style and the demographic profile in terms of educational attainment was not rejected, while age and length of services, was rejected.

Table 11. Respondents' Leadership Style in terms of Democratic and Demographic Profile

Variables	Democratic Leadership Style		Remarks	Decision
	X^2 (df)	p-value		
Age	32.923 ^{ns} (24)	0.106	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Educational attainment	8.062 ^{ns} (16)	0.947	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Length of service	50.116* (32)	0.022	Significant	Reject H ₀

Note: 3 – based on Chi-square Test ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns - $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

Table 11 displays the relationship between the respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style and demographic profile. The result showed that the respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style had a significant correlation with their demographic profile in terms of length of service. A study by Lee et al. (2021), entitled "The Moderating Effect of Leader Tenure on the Relationship Between Leadership Style and Employee Outcomes" found that leaders with longer tenures were more likely to adopt a democratic leadership style. They theorized that experience allowed leaders to trust their team's capabilities and delegate more, fostering a democratic environment.

Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated no significant relationship between the respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style and the demographic profile in terms of age and educational attainment were not rejected, while length of services, was rejected.

Problem 4: Which of the demographic profile significantly predict the leadership style of the respondents?

Table 12 presents the variables that best predict respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style. The result showed that the respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style was not affected by the demographic profile. This implied that no variables affected the respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style. The non-significant impact of demographic variables on leadership style suggested that factors beyond demographics played a more substantial role in shaping transformational leadership behaviors. These findings underscored the importance of considering contextual and situational factors in leadership research

and practice. Research by Bass and Riggio (2019) suggested that effective leadership extended beyond demographic attributes and encompassed a broader spectrum of behavioral, cognitive, and emotional factors.

Table 12. Variables4 that best predict Respondents' Leadership Style in terms of Transformational Style

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.278	0.206		15.919	0.000
Age	0.123	0.070	0.223	1.770	0.080
Educational Attainment	-0.079	0.064	-0.123	-1.233	0.221
Length of Service	-0.011	0.045	-0.029	-0.233	0.816
R = 0.232	R² = 0.054	F = 1.816	Sig. = 0.149		

Note: 4 – based on Linear Regression ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns - P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

The R2 value of 0.054 implied that 5.4% of the variance in leadership style in terms of transformational style could be explained by their demographic profile. Hence, 96.6% of the respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style difference could be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis was not significant, with an F-value of 1.816 with a corresponding p-value of 0.149. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there was no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' leadership style in terms of transformational style” was not rejected.

Table 13 displays the variables that best predict respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style. The result showed that the respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style was not affected by the demographic profile. This implied that no variables affected the respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style. This suggested that other factors beyond demographic characteristics may be more influential in shaping transactional leadership behaviors. Recent research by Avolio and Bass (2018) suggested that contextual factors, such as organizational culture and situational demands might override demographic influences on leadership style.

Table 13. Variables5 that best predict Respondents' Leadership Style in terms of Transactional Style

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.816	0.247		11.405	0.000
Age	0.094	0.084	0.145	1.130	0.261
Educational Attainment	-0.059	0.077	-0.077	-0.763	0.447
Length of Service	-0.042	0.054	-0.099	-0.771	0.443
R = 0.133	R² = 0.018	F = 0.579	Sig. = 0.630		

Note: 5 – based on Linear Regression ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns - P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

The R2 value of 0.018 implied that 1.8% of the variance in leadership style in terms of transactional style could be explained by their demographic profile. Hence, 98.2% of the respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style difference could be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis was not significant, with an F-value of 0.579 with a corresponding p-value of 0.630. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that “there was no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' leadership style in terms of transactional style” was not rejected.

Table 14 exhibits the variables that best predict respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style. The result showed that the respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style was affected by the demographic profile in terms of length of service. This implied that only the length of service affected the respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style.

This was in line with the research of Avolio et al (2019) which states that leaders with longer service might feel more secure delegating tasks and involving others in decision-making due to their accumulated knowledge and experience.

Table 14. Variables6 that best predict Respondents' Leadership Style in terms of Democratic Style

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.531	0.215		16.427	0.000
Age	-0.093	0.073	-0.161	-1.277	0.205
Educational Attainment	-0.060	0.067	-0.089	-0.901	0.370
Length of Service	0.107	0.047	0.285	2.271	0.025
R = 0.245	R² = 0.060	F = 2.044	Sig. = 0.113		

Note: 6 – based on Linear Regression ** - P < 0.01 *** - P < 0.001 ns - P > 0.05 * - P < 0.05

The R2 value of 0.060 implied that 6.0% of the variance in leadership style in terms of democratic style could be explained by their demographic profile. Hence, 94% of the respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style difference could be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis was not significant, with an F-value of 2.044 with a corresponding p-value of 0.113. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there was no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' leadership style in terms of democratic style" was rejected in terms of length of service.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following are prompted:

The study highlighted the prevalence of transformational leadership among female Maranao school heads in Lanao del Norte Division. These leaders tended to use inspiration or empathy to engage followers. They were known to possess courage, confidence, and the willingness to make sacrifices for the greater good.

Additionally, findings suggested that leadership styles were influenced by demographic factors, particularly length of service, indicating the evolution of leadership approaches over time.

Understanding were leadership preferences and practices of female Maranao school heads was crucial for promoting effective leadership development and organizational effectiveness within the educational landscape. By recognizing the predominant leadership style and its correlations with demographic variables, stakeholders could tailor support and training programs to enhance leadership competencies and address needs within the educational sector.

In light of the findings, as mentioned above and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

School Head should participate in leadership workshops or seminars to develop their own leadership skills and understand the importance of democratic leadership in fostering inclusivity and collaboration.

Enhancing leadership abilities should be the main objective of training programs for school administrators. This will enable the heads of the schools to effectively inspire and motivate their staff and people.

Teachers show support to their school heads for the improvement their leadership style.

Professional development opportunities can be offered to teachers to enhance their understanding of various leadership and how they can contribute to a positive school culture.

The survey questionnaire shall have the same total number of indicators.

Further research could explore the effectiveness of different leadership styles in diverse educational contexts, considering cultural factors and societal norms.

Fostering a culture of inclusive and participative leadership within educational institutions can contribute to creating nurturing environments conducive to student learning and staff development.

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